

BuildingSmart Use-Case Definition – Risk-Based Status Assessment Use Case With Key Performance Indicators Dashboard

Section 1: MetaData

1.1 Identification of the document

Title:

*RISK-BASED STATUS ASSESSMENT USE CASE WITH KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS
DASHBOARD*

ASHVIN: Assistants for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin.

Short Text:

Prediction different maintenance scenarios for infrastructure assets based on inspection and monitoring predicated on different performance indicators such as time and budget

Project Status:

Finished

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N/A

Author:

Eser Senturk (Technische Universität Berlin), Mary Lidiya Kennedy (Technische Universität Berlin)

Introduction:

This document provides background and describes a use case of interactively review and utilise specific outputs of the risk assessment and the consequence modelling in risk analysis to choose the optimal maintenance scenario for the maintenance of the asset using asset management key performance indicators.

1.2 Imprint:

Project Group:

TUB, INFRAPLAN

Partners:

Timo Hartmann(Technische Universität Berlin), Irina Stipanovic(Infra Plan konzalting)

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N/A

Section 2: Use-Case Definition

2.1 Data Sheets & Standards

N/A

2.2 General Definition of the Use-Case

USE CASE DESCRIPTION	
Title	Risk-Based Status Assessment Use Case With Key Performance Indicators Dashboard
Goal	To predict risk-based maintenance scenarios for asset management predicated on the inspections and monitoring image data throughout its life cycle
Description	To review and utilise specific outputs of the risk assessment and the consequence modelling in risk analysis analysis to choose the optimal maintenance scenario for the maintenance of the asset using asset management key performance indicators.
Input Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Probability of failure of assets based on asset monitoring data and assessment founded on defect detection with identified damages, and their potential failure modes • Risk approach preferred • Traffic intensity (in case of transportation infrastructure) • Available budget, Total revenue/asset value E • Estimated available budget per year for regular maintenance • Time available for maintenance works
Sequence of actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Obtain the probability of failure of the particular asset under study based on monitoring and condition assessment of the asset which varies depending on the type of infrastructure under study and types of infrastructure defects of interest 2. Set forth the parameters for maintenance scenarios such as available budget, total asset value, usage intensity (in the case of transportation infrastructure), and time available. 3. Collect historical and current data on nominal main different necessary maintenance activities including inspection, their accompanying frequencies and their estimated unit cost. The unit cost of a certain maintenance activity (AUCi), which includes workers and machines costs, is multiplied by the quantity of units of that activity (Aqi). 4. Estimate discount rate to determine life cycle costs from inflation and interest rate data 5. Estimate initial construction costs, nominal maintenance costs for year t and nominal end-of-life costs to determine Life Cycle Costs which is the sum of the mentioned costs. 6. Calculate initial construction costs based on the data on design and planning costs as well as direct construction costs such as materials, labour, and equipment expenses from the bill of quantities and also from the BIM model. 7. Calculate end-of-life costs from the information about the predicted service life of used materials / components, but it should be regularly updated with the information collected through inspection and monitoring. 8. Create a maintenance schedule to determine maintenance costs for each year. 9. Estimate indirect costs which is summation of user delay costs and environmental costs. 10. Collect data about travel distance and extra travel time caused by maintenance activities should be determined by traffic flow models to determine user delay costs 11. Costs, the quantities of materials and machines can be collected from the bill of quantities from maintenance design project or BIM models to calculate environmental costs. 12. The risk of failure of the asset is then estimated based on the parameters calculated (direct and indirect costs) and from the determined probability of failure and its potential mode of failure as following: The proposed framework once established, the asset

	managers can set up different scenarios in terms available budget, time available for maintenance and analyse the risk and possible maintenance strategies.
Primary actors	Asset owners or managers.
Secondary actors	Maintenance engineers, structural engineers
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The conditions of the asset under consideration should be monitored and assessed • Probability of failure should be calculated for the proposed use case
Trigger	Development of well-assessed and condition-based maintenance scenarios for predictive maintenance resulting in resource efficiency, reduced costs for maintenance, productivity, and safety at the construction sites.
Post-conditions	
Frequency of use	Throughout the lifecycle of the asset- especially during its maintenance cycle
Support planned for	ASHVIN
UC Created by	INFCON
Date of last update	

Figure 1 Use Case Description

Aim and Scope:

The proposed use case aims to present the asset managers with different maintenance scenarios based on the monitoring and condition assessment of the asset mainly utilizing image monitoring data from the site, taking into account the asset management defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), including safety, costs, productivity and environmental cost, to find the optimal maintenance scenarios to be performed within the determined time.

The use case also aims to aid the asset managers in understanding, how the data associated with assets can be acquired, populated, and employed to make decisions to increase efficiency, productivity, safety, and reduced cost of construction projects.

Objectives:

An application as proposed in the current use case enables asset managers, maintenance engineers, structural engineers and business partners to find optimal maintenance scenarios for their respective assets in terms of their preferred key performance indicators such as increased productivity, resource efficiency, safety at the sites and reduced costs. The use case also aims to aid the asset managers in understanding, how the data associated with assets can be acquired, populated, and employed to make decisions to increase efficiency, productivity, safety, and reduced cost of construction projects.

j - month of the year

k - the occurrence order number of the day of the week

n - the number of days of that day of the week during that month.

In the next step, collate data on costs associated with the asset maintenance. This can be divided into two main categories, direct ones, which are directly born by the owner during the entire life span of an asset and indirect costs which are related to the society, to the end users, environment, community etc. Since they are occurring along the whole life cycle of a structure, it is important to develop a Life Cycle Cost Model (LCCM) for the cost estimation of different maintenance alternatives. The main objective of the LCCM is to determine direct and indirect impacts (or costs) of planned and unplanned disruptions causing inspections and maintenance activities, which can then be used for the comparison of different maintenance strategies.

1. Direct costs

Costs associated with design and construction, maintenance, and end-of-life are the three categories into which direct agency/owner costs are typically subdivided.

(a) Calculation of maintenance cost:

For data collection of maintenance cost: The unit costs for each equipment and workers have to be collected for each country individually by collection of historical data or through surveys. The required data about the quantities of materials and machines can be collected from the bill of quantities from maintenance design project. The information about the construction machines usage (actual travel distance and duration of works) can be collected from GPS tracking devices. Data about the duration of different activities can be collected by the usage of WT901 WIFI or WTGAHRS2 sensors, which are mounted on the equipment on construction site to gather data about the movement.

For the calculation of maintenance costs first the maintenance scenario that most accurately describes the estimated required maintenance over the life cycle of the object has to be determined. This means determining the different necessary maintenance activities including inspections, their accompanying frequencies, and their estimated unit costs. Next, the unit cost of a certain maintenance activity (AUC_i), which includes workers and machines costs, is multiplied by the quantity of units related to that activity (Aq_i). All the years in the asset's life cycle during which that maintenance action occurs are given credit for the associated annual maintenance cost (based on the frequency attributed to that activity).

The maintenance costs for one specific year are therefore calculated by:

$$MC_{t,nom} = \sum_{i=n}^m AUC_i \times Aq_i$$

Wherein:

$MC_{t, nom}$ = nominal maintenance costs for year t (€)

i = activity n until m

AUC = activity unit cost of activity i (€/unit)

Aqi = quantity of units for activity i in year t (unit)

The total maintenance costs for the object during its life cycle is therefore calculated by:

$$MC_{tot,disc} = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{MC_{t,nom}}{(1+r)^t} \times (1+\chi)$$

Wherein:

MC_{tot, disc} = the total maintenance costs during the life cycle of the object (€)

MC_{t, nom} = maintenance costs for year t (€)

t = year in life cycle from 0 until end of life cycle T

r = the discount rate (%)

χ = an additional percentage to cover unassigned, indirect, engineering, and other costs.

(b) Calculation of discount rate:

For adoption of appropriate discount rate The adoption of an appropriate discount rate that reflects historical trends over lengthy periods of time is stressed heavily by the FHWA (1998) as well as the majority of guidance on the choice of discount rate. Average and recorded historic rates should serve as the basis when deciding upon the discount rate for the analysis

Discount rate has significant impact on the ultimate Life Cycle Cost (LCC) result. Discount rate represents the real value of money over time, and it affects how future cash flows would affect the overall LCC. Multiple variables are required to calculate the discount rate's impact, mainly the present-day activity cost, the number of discount periods and the discount factor. The real discount rate can be estimated using the derived formula.

$$r = \frac{i-f}{1+f}$$

Where:

f = Inflation rate

i = Nominal interest rate

r = Real discount rate—an interest rate that has been adjusted to remove the effect of expected or actual inflation

(c) **Calculation of Life Cycle Costs (LCC):**

Life cycle costs include all maintenance and repair activities during whole life cycle of a structure together with initial construction costs and end of life for different scenarios. Depending on the level of analysis it can include direct or/and indirect costs. Direct costs are initial construction costs (€), nominal maintenance costs for year t (€) and nominal end-of-life costs (€)

(d) **Calculation of initial construction costs (ICC):**

Initial construction costs include design and planning costs as well as direct construction costs such as materials, labour, and equipment expenses. The initial construction costs are calculated by the following:

$$ICC = \sum_{i=n}^m CUC_i \times Cq_i \times (1 + \chi)$$

Wherein:

ICC = initial construction costs (€)

i = construction element n until element m

CUC $_i$ = construction unit cost of element i (€/unit)

Cq $_i$ = the quantity of construction element i present in the design (unit)

χ = an additional percentage to cover unassigned, indirect, engineering and other costs.

(e) **Calculation of end-of-life costs:**

The end-of-life costs include the costs of demolition and disposal minus the residual value and are calculated in the same manner as initial construction costs. The structure is divided into constituent elements with a unit cost for end-of-life and the amount of a certain building element is multiplied with the corresponding end-of-life unit cost. The equation is as follows:

$$EoLC_{disc} = \frac{EoLC_{T,nom}}{(1+r)^T} = \frac{\sum_{i=n}^m DUC_i \times Cq_i}{(1+r)^T}$$

Wherein:

EoLC $_{nom}$ = nominal end-of-life costs (€)

EoLC $_{disc}$ = are the discounted end-of-life costs (€)

i = construction element n until element m

DUC $_i$ = demolition and disposal unit cost for element i (€/unit)

C_{qi} = the quantity of construction element i present in the design (unit)

T = year in which life cycle ends

r = discount factor (%)

Data about the quantities for initial construction costs are taken from the bill of quantities - as detailed as available at the design stage. The data can be then updated from the digital twin models.

For the calculation for maintenance costs over the life cycle, it is necessary to predict the service life of each unit / element, and these data can be updated based on the inspection and monitoring data. End of life costs require the information about the predicted service life of used materials / components, but it should be regularly updated with the information collected through inspection and monitoring.

2. Indirect Costs:

Indirect costs are comprised of user delay costs and environmental cost. It can be estimated as follows:

(a) User delay Costs:

User delay costs are usually determined for the transport infrastructure networks. The calculation methods presented here are applicable for road networks, but they can be adapted for railway, waterway, or airport infrastructure.

To calculate user delay costs data about travel distance and extra travel time caused by maintenance activities should be determined by traffic flow models. Value of time should be determined from national statistical data. Data about the usage intensity (e.g. AADT) can be collected from traffic monitoring stations

The equations used for determining the user delay cost are based on the work of Sundquist & Karoumi (2012). The total user costs are a summation of the two sub-categories: freight delay costs and passengers delay costs. Because the user costs are made during the life cycle of the structure, future cash flows will have to be discounted to determine a total present value.

$$UDC_{tot, disc} = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{TDC_{fr,t,nom}}{(1+r)^t} + \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{TDC_{car,t,nom}}{(1+r)^t}$$

Wherein:

$UDC_{tot, disc}$ = total discounted user delay costs (€)

t = year in life cycle from 0 until end-of-life cycle T

r = discount factor (%)

TDC_{fr,t, nom} = nominal freight traffic delay costs in year t (€)
 TDC_{car,t, nom} = nominal commuters traffic delay costs in year t (€)

The traffic delay costs are the costs that represent the valuable time of the network users itself. This economic value of the user's time is dependent on several factors. The type of traffic (passenger vehicle or freight traffic), the amount of persons/cargo per vehicle and the type of cargo/person (business/leisure). The input data for the calculation of traffic delay costs should come from analysis of traffic flow models. The traffic delay costs can be then determined by:

$$TDC_t = ETT \times ADT_t \times VOT_{user} \times N_t$$

Wherein:

TDC_t = traffic delay costs for year t (€), calculated separately for freight and for passenger cars,

ETT = extra travel time per type of users (hours)

ADT_t = the average daily traffic (separately for freight and for passenger cars) in year t passing the analysed section or bridge in question (PCE/day)

VOT_{user} = is a monetary value for the users time (€/hour), different values for different user groups, e.g. freight, business, leisure,

N_t = the duration of a certain maintenance activity for year t (days).

(b) Environmental Costs:

To calculate environmental costs the quantities of materials and machines can be collected from the bill of quantities from maintenance design project or BIM models. The information about the construction machines usage (actual travel distance and duration of works) can be collected from GPS tracking devices.

In the analysis, first the environmental impact of one kg of material is determined as a basic parameter of the model. Those values are then used to calculate the total environmental impact by multiplying it by the amount of material present in the construction or maintenance activity. The total environmental costs can then be determined using the following equation.

$$EC = \sum_{i=1}^m EE_i \times ECI_i$$

Wherein:

EC = environmental costs (€/functional unit, €/kg, €/m² or €/total)

EE_i = environmental effects for impact category i (kg of impact category equivalent (ICEq)/functional unit (one bridge))

ECI_i = the environmental cost indicator for environmental effect category i (€/kg of ICEq)

i = environmental impact category n until m

Environmental costs incurred during the life cycle of the structure are not discounted as recommended by (Hellweg et al., 2003). The environmental effects per impact category can be determined using the following equation:

$$EE_i = \sum EE_{i,j} \times M_{qj}$$

Wherein:

EE_i = environmental effects for impact category i (kg of impact category equivalent (kg ICeq)/functional unit)

$EE_{i,j}$ = environmental effect for impact category i per kg of material j (kg ICeq/kg material)

M_{qj} = material quantity per functional unit for material j (kg material/functional unit)
j = the different materials n until m

From the calculated direct and indirect costs, risk of failure can be calculated using the following formula:

$$R = p_{FM} \times Consequences = p_{FM} \times (DC + IC)$$

Where:

p_{FM} - probability of an asset failure mode given the threat scenario magnitude

DC +IC - direct and indirect consequences i.e. monetized losses due to the failure mode for certain element / object / system

The user can now assess the risk of failure of the asset based on different maintenance scenarios. The scenarios also encompass the probable consequences that follows, if the user choose one particular scenario for every scenario presented on the dashboard. Each scenario can be also compared based on nNPV, and Benefit Cost ratio per scenario if maintenance costs are of utmost importance for the user. This methodology also facilitates calculation of future risk with the help of deterioration curve of the asset or the object, and consequence if a certain maintenance performed or not. The current use case was applied and demonstrated on a real case, a part of the runway at Zadar airport. Further details of the implementation of the use case are given in the following section.

#3 Implementation of RISA at Zadar Airport, Croatia

Zadar Airport is situated in the middle of the Adriatic coast, and in 2019 was among the top 5 in terms of traffic growth(+37,6% increase in passenger traffic EUROPE Airport Traffic Report, (www.aci-europe.org), Therefore, the airport is going to be extended and reconstructed. The project is planned to be executed in several phases. The first phase started in 2021, which includes the extension of the runway, and expansion of the terminal building and apron. The next phase includes construction of the new passenger terminal, for which the design project has been finished. The digital twin asset management tool was used to improve the overall operational and maintenance management, consequently, optimize the resources spending and improve safety. A network-wide digital twin would also help ensure that maintenance on one section of highway does not coincide with works on alternative routes.

A BIM-digital twin was developed containing detailed structure information about the runway layout i, materials, drainage systems and signage. It was combined with the Airport Operational Database (AODB) and inspection data performed with Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). Deep machine learning techniques were then applied on drone-based images for the automation of the visual inspection and damage detection procedures.

The first step in the methodology for the current demonstration projects is the determination of the runway condition index, which is following ASTM for Airport Pavement Condition Index Surveys. During the visual inspection of runway, taxiway and apron areas pre-categorized and grouped distresses are recorded, with their location and quantity. Same process is performed while using UAVs, focusing on the pre-dominant types of defects, caused by load, climate, and/or poor construction, or a combination of these in a form of cracks (D1), repaired cracks (D2) and construction joints (D3). Based on the expert judgment, the level of severity of the recorded defects were categorised in three groups, low, medium and high, in order to determine the Deduct Value (DV) and, finally Pavement Condition Index (PCI) for each sample unit, following the ASTM methodology, as follows:

PCI represents a numerical rating of the pavement condition that ranges from 0 to 100, with 0 being the worst possible condition and 100 being the best possible condition based on the detection of defects on the pavement's surface; the runway condition index gives a measure of the pavement's current condition. The structural capacity cannot be directly measured by this index, but it offers a rational and impartial basis for choosing the most important maintenance and repair tasks. Rating scale for the PCI, as a percentage of the sample area with certain defect classes detected. Fig 6 shows categorisation of runway condition using the adopted PCI rating based on detected defects cracks, repaired cracks and construction joints.

The methodology developed as part of this use case aims with the help of frame developed as part bSI use case GIS integrator for digital-twin-based asset management first detect different types of surface defects enclosed in visual data, collected through a UAV scanning mission over the runway area. The current methodology can be categorized into two steps, in the first phase a UAV is employed to perform a coverage mission across the runway and collect RGB images depicting surface defects. The acquired image data is then processed and annotated according, to labelling the defect instances of interest. This data is used to train a sophisticated CNN model

that semantically segments the input images collected from the site and produces an annotated mask where the detected defects are segmented accordingly so that in future, it can predict the condition of the asset. In the second phase the acquired images are processed by the model and a prediction mask is provided, where the detected defects are highlighted. Information about the location, the number the type and the size of detected defects can be extracted from the segmented outcome. Furthermore, the acquired RGB data can be exploited to generate an orthomosaic representation of the scanned area, which can be used to create a digital representation map of the runway infrastructure. The combination of the above individual elements in a consolidated digital map allows to estimate the severity level of the inspected damages and allows objective and digital monitoring of their evolution over time. Overall, the proposed framework can comprise a decision support system that enables the automation of the inspection process and optimizes maintenance planning by scheduling targeted maintenance operations.

As explained earlier, the acquired and annotated data along with the historic data was used to perform damage detection based on the ML model developed. Thereby calculating the probability of failure of the asset.

Figure 3 Map of the runway with GIS positioned photographs and the results of the defect detection method.

The probability of failure of the asset as calculated based on the bSI use case GIS integrator for digital-twin-based asset management is a pre-requisite for risk assessment of the runway under study. The following parameter were then provided generating the maintenance scenarios and calculating the risk.

- Risk approach,
- Traffic intensity: Future scenario
- Maintenance unit costs(for going out into the field equipment)
- Time available for maintenance works(night,day)
- Total revenue/ asset value
- Estimated available budget per year for maintenance

Risk approach	<input type="text" value="Small investment"/>
Traffic intensity: Future scenarios	<input type="text" value="High"/>
Maintenance unit costs (for going out into the field with equipment)	€ <input type="text" value="500"/>
Time available for maintenance works (night, day) – in hours	<input type="text" value="5"/>
Total revenue / asset value	€ <input type="text" value="5.000.000"/>
Estimated available budget	
Per year – regular maintenance	€ <input type="text" value="10.000"/>
Per investment period (e.g. 10 years) – bigger maintenance, replacement, etc.	€ <input type="text" value="200.000"/>

Figure 4 User interface for acquiring input from user

Then the use case generates different maintenance scenarios based on the Key Performance Indicators and other relevant inputs from the user to present user with different maintenance strategies. It also points out the consequences of the damage detected over the years as shown in Fig 6

Figure 5 Maintenance Scenario Example

	Maintenance Scenario	Maintenance Cost (EUR/m)		Deduct value
1	Do nothing + monitor		1	0<20
2	Crack seal	200	2	20-40
3	Partial crack repair	500	3	40-60
4	Full depth crack repair	1500	4	60-100

Figure 6 Maintenance scenario with maintenance costs

Figure 7 Categorization of runway condition using adopted PCI rating based on detected defects cracks, repaired cracks and construction joints

Figure 8 Risk Analysis

Fig 10 shows some scenarios generated for the maintenance strategies that can be adopted for the Zadar airport based on the user input and the consequences of the damages, along with the consequences of adopting different scenarios for the asset, which enables the risk analysis possible with the available budget.

Figure 9 Different scenarios based on user preferences

The scenarios are then shown on the dashboard, which the user can interact with and see different scenarios and their consequences.

Figure 10 Maintenance scenarios - geopositioned

ASHVIN IMPACT ON ZADAR DEMONSTRATION PROJECT

Performance indicators	Unit	How to measure	Proposed integration into Digital Twin
Key Performance Indicator: Productivity			
Duration of maintenance works	h, days	Duration of maintenance activities affects users and operational planning. Maintenance interventions	Maintenance time: comparison of different maintenance options (e.g. Minor repair vs. major

		require partial closures or full closures of a runway. Time required for a maintenance intervention is time that the runway closed completely or closed for a certain type of aircraft.	repair – duration of traffic closure records
Unavailability of the asset during the maintenance / inspection works	m, or section	Runway or section which can't be used or partly used (decreased length/width, less availability) compared to undisturbed normal usage.	Cameras, Traffic data (# of planes per day, type of planes, passengers, cargo...) No of passengers per year for Zadar airport
Usage intensity (before, during and after the intervention)	Average annual daily or monthly traffic data	Traffic data can be used in different forms for example for the whole year or for a part of the year to quantify the importance of an airport, or the importance of an airport in a certain period (e.g. Zadar airport very busy in summer) or to calculate owners cost/loss.	Cameras, Traffic data (# of planes per day, type of planes, passengers, cargo...)
Service life of maintenance solution	years	Monitoring of maintenance measure performance (drones) to determine for how long the intervention performs at the required level	Drones, sensors (e.g. optical fibers, corrosion sensor) Meteo data (humidity, temperature)
Key Performance Indicator: Resource Efficiency			
Environmental impacts related to the usage of materials and machines in maintenance solutions	CO2, SO2, PO43, Sb,... €/kg, m2, unit or total	Different environmental impact categories per kg of material and fuel for machines used for a certain maintenance activity, data about quantities, materials source, technology, transport data are used as inputs in LCA model from design project.	LCA model outputs Graphical representation (of comparison results)

Key Performance Indicator: cost			
Maintenance Cost	€/m ² , unit or total	Includes cost of equipment, energy, and workforce. Comparison drone vs. conventional inspection	Cost data over time, graphs
User delay cost	€/min, h	Costs of unavailability of the asset for the owner or end-user caused by inspection or maintenance activities. For airports can be different for different periods through the year.	Cost data per activity Can be visualized based on traffic data and duration time
Total LCC	€/kg, m ² , unit or total	Life cycle costs are costs occurring during whole life cycle of a structure including end of life for different scenarios. For calculation of LCC a life cycle scenario needs to be developed with prospects of deterioration and timing of certain maintenance interventions.	Annual cost per scenario Total Costs
Environmental cost	€/kg, m ² , unit or total	Monetized environmental impacts related to the usage of materials and machines during maintenance	Cost data over environmental impact category, graphs

2.4 Disciplines:

Investigation discipline- risk assessment.

Project Management discipline- cost estimation, proposal preparation, and scheduling

2.5 Life Cycle Stages

Operation and maintenance

Section 3: Process-definition

*Life cycle stages: post-construction stage
Operation and maintenance*

Section 4: Exchange Requirements

The current section gives a brief description of the data exchange requirements for utilizing the current use case.

Figure 11 Exchange Requirements

Section 5: Change Log

This is a section only for changes made after publishing to the front end